

GUIDANCE DOCUMENT

Policy for Evaluating Impact of Viral Mutations on COVID-19 Tests (Revised)

Guidance for Test Developers and Food and Drug Administration Staff

JANUARY 2023

Final

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Guidance Documents (</regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents>)

Docket Number:

[FDA-2020-D-0987](https://www.regulations.gov/docket/FDA-2020-D-0987) (<https://www.regulations.gov/docket/FDA-2020-D-0987>).

Issued by:

</regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/policy-evaluating-impact-viral-mutations-covid-19-tests-revised>).

Center for Devices and Radiological Health

March 24, 2023 - The FDA has finalized two guidances: *[Transition Plan for Medical Devices That Fall Within Enforcement Policies Issued During the Coronavirus Disease 2019 \(COVID-19\) Public Health Emergency](/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/transition-plan-medical-devices-fall-within-enforcement-policies-issued-during-coronavirus-disease)* (</regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/transition-plan-medical-devices-fall-within-enforcement-policies-issued-during-coronavirus-disease>) and *[Transition Plan for Medical Devices Issued Emergency Use Authorizations \(EUAs\) Related to Coronavirus Disease 2019 \(COVID-19\)](/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/transition-plan-medical-devices-issued-emergency-use-authorizations-euas-related-coronavirus-disease)* (</regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/transition-plan-medical-devices-issued-emergency-use-authorizations-euas-related-coronavirus-disease>). The guidances outline the FDA's general recommendations to transition from certain policies adopted and operations implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic to normal operations, including the FDA's recommendations for:

- Developing a transition implementation plan,
- Submitting a marketing submission, and
- Taking other actions with respect to these devices.

The FDA encourages stakeholders to review the two final guidances, attend the webinar, and reach out to the FDA if they have questions or concerns. In particular, for manufacturers planning to seek marketing authorization for their devices, the FDA recommends beginning work on a marketing submission, including a transition implementation plan, as described in the guidances.

Additional Resources:

- [Transition Plan for Medical Devices That Fall Within Enforcement Policies Issued During the Coronavirus Disease 2019 \(COVID-19\) Public Health Emergency. \(/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/transition-plan-medical-devices-fall-within-enforcement-policies-issued-during-coronavirus-disease\)](#)
- [Transition Plan for Medical Devices Issued Emergency Use Authorizations \(EUAs\) Related to Coronavirus Disease 2019 \(COVID-19\). \(/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/transition-plan-medical-devices-issued-emergency-use-authorizations-euas-related-coronavirus-disease\)](#)
- [Webinar on Guidances on COVID-19 Transition Plans for Medical Devices - April 18, 2023 \(https://public4.pagefreezer.com/browse/FDA/01-03-2024T13:19/https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/workshops-conferences-medical-devices-unpublished/webinar-guidances-covid-19-transition-plans-medical-devices-04182023\)](#) [\(http://www.fda.gov/about-fda/website-policies/website-disclaimer\)](#)

FDA plays a critical role in protecting the United States from threats such as emerging infectious diseases, including the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. FDA is committed to providing timely guidance to support response efforts to this pandemic.

FDA is issuing this guidance to provide a policy and recommendations on evaluating the potential impact of emerging and future viral mutations of SARS-CoV-2 on COVID-19 tests. This guidance describes a policy for test developers to consider the impact of emerging and future variants on their COVID-19 tests during development and post-authorization. Throughout this guidance, references to COVID-19 tests are referring to molecular and antigen tests that detect the SARS-CoV-2 virus and serology tests that detect antibodies to the SARS-CoV-2 virus.

This policy is intended to remain in effect only for the duration of the declaration under section 564 of the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FD&C Act) by the Secretary of Health and Human Services (HHS) on February 4, 2020, declaring that circumstances exist justifying the

authorization of emergency use of in vitro diagnostics for detection and/or diagnosis of the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV). FDA continues to assess the evolving situation and intends to update this guidance as appropriate.

Submit Comments

Submit Comments Online (<https://www.regulations.gov/docket/FDA-2020-D-0987/document>)

You can submit online or written comments on any guidance at any time (see 21 CFR 10.115(g)(5))

If unable to submit comments online, please mail written comments to:

Dockets Management
Food and Drug Administration
5630 Fishers Lane, Rm 1061
Rockville, MD 20852

All written comments should be identified with this document's docket number: [FDA-2020-D-0987](https://www.regulations.gov/docket/FDA-2020-D-0987)
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